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The Role of Business in Promoting Sustainable Development in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the role of business in promoting sustainable development in Nigeria. The objective of the study was to investigate the role of job creation on sustainable development in Nigeria. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study was anchored on Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 1,150,000 businesses in Rivers State. The sample size was of 400 obtained using Taro Yamane Statistical Tool. Purposive sampling techniques was adopted. A total of 400 copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents. 283 copies representing 71% were retrieved. The data was analysed using mean and standard deviation. All tests for the study were carried out using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The hypotheses were tested using Spearman's Rank order correlation coefficient at a significance level of 0.05. Findings revealed a moderate positive relationship between job creation and sustainable development. It also revealed a strong positive relationship between economic progress and sustainable development. Furthermore, it revealed a moderate positive relationship between wealth creation and sustainable development. The study concluded that businesses significantly influence sustainable development by generating employment opportunities, stimulating economic growth, and facilitating inclusive wealth distribution. It was recommended among others that government and business leaders should collaborate to expand job opportunities through support for small and medium enterprises.

Keywords: Role, business, promoting sustainable development, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development has emerged as a vital global objective aimed at balancing economic growth, environmental protection, and social inclusion. In Nigeria, a country dealing with a number of developmental challenges, including poverty, unemployment, environmental degradation, and infrastructural deficits, the role of companies in promoting sustainable development has become more significant. Companies in Nigeria are significant economic actors that, in addition to creating jobs and revenue, have the ability to encourage environmental stewardship and social change. The private sector is well-positioned to assist government efforts in accomplishing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the UN in a developing nation like Nigeria, where state resources are inadequate to solve widespread socioeconomic difficulties (Adeleke et al., 2022).

The socioeconomic trajectory of Nigeria is greatly influenced by firms that integrate sustainability into their operations, strategy, and corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives. Adopting sustainable business practices, such as reducing carbon footprints, ensuring ethical labour standards, investing in community development, and supporting renewable energy projects, can mitigate the business and

industrial operations' negative social and environmental effects (Okonkwo & Udeh, 2021). Businesses in Nigeria are increasingly understanding the connection between social and environmental responsibility and sustainable profitability. To address stakeholder concerns and enhance their social licence to operate, oil and gas corporations, which have historically been associated with environmental damage and community strife, have begun implementing sustainability frameworks (Nwankwo & Eze, 2023).

Companies are also growing more aware of their impact on society and the environment, as evidenced by the promotion of corporate sustainability reporting in Nigeria by the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria and other regulatory bodies. In addition to improving accountability and transparency, companies that disclose their sustainability performance also win over investors, customers, and host communities (Adegbite & Nakajima, 2020). This shift to greater corporate accountability is essential in a country like Nigeria, where institutional weaknesses and bad governance regularly undermine public trust. Therefore, ethical businesses that promote sustainability could act as moral leadership role models and advance the nation.

Additionally, businesses may promote innovation and fair economic growth by investing in green technology, sustainable agriculture, and the concepts of the circular economy. For instance, the emergence of fintech and green firms in Nigeria demonstrates how entrepreneurship may promote financial inclusion, environmental preservation, and job creation (Obi & Afolabi, 2022). Similarly, large companies may support SMEs by putting inclusive supply chains and capacity-building programmes into place, which will make regional economies more resilient. Such inclusive business models are especially relevant in Nigeria's economy, which is dominated by the unorganised sector and where access to cash, markets, and technology is still limited.

In order to achieve sustainable development, the Nigerian government has emphasised the importance of multi-stakeholder collaboration through initiatives such as the Nigerian Sustainable Development Action Plan and the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP). In this scenario, businesses' duties go beyond making money to include actively advancing the nation's development through partnerships with international development partners, civil society organisations, and governmental entities (UNDP Nigeria, 2023). Corruption, inconsistent policies, inadequate infrastructure, and Nigerian companies' ignorance of sustainability are some of the problems that impede progress. The establishment of a supportive environment that motivates businesses to align their operations with national and international sustainability goals is essential to overcoming these challenges. Based on this background, this study seeks to examine the role of business in promoting sustainable development in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the growing recognition of the private sector's role in advancing sustainable development in Nigeria, significant challenges continue to hinder the full integration of sustainability principles into business operations. Even while a large number of Nigerian companies participate in some kind of CSR, these initiatives are frequently dispersed, ill-coordinated, and not strategically in line with the more general objectives of sustainable development. Many businesses still just think about maximising profits, paying little attention to social justice, environmental preservation, or long-term economic viability. This has worsened long-standing problems including pollution, resource depletion, unethical labour practices, and growing regional socioeconomic gaps.

Furthermore, there is a dearth of thorough information and knowledge on the ways in which various company types from startups to global conglomerates actually support or undermine sustainable development in Nigeria. Studies that already exist frequently generalise the role of firms without accounting for geographical differences or industry-specific facts that might affect sustainability outcomes. Furthermore, it is challenging to assess how well businesses contribute to national development goals due to a lack of institutional enforcement and a lack of understanding and acceptance of international sustainability frameworks.

With its targeted analysis of how Nigerian companies may move from ancillary CSR initiatives to integrating sustainability as a fundamental operational and strategic value, this research aims to close the knowledge gap. It seeks to investigate certain behaviours, obstacles, and facilitators that impact this shift

in order to offer a more sophisticated comprehension of the relationship between business and sustainability in the Nigerian.

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1.1: Conceptual framework showing role of business and sustainable development.

Source:

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to examine the role of business in promoting sustainable development in Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. investigate the role of job creation on sustainable development in Nigeria.
2. examine the role of economic progress on sustainable development in Nigeria.
3. determine the role of wealth creation on sustainable development in Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the role of job creation on sustainable development in Nigeria?
2. What is the role of economic progress on sustainable development in Nigeria?
3. What is the role of wealth creation on sustainable development in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses was formulated and tested in the study:

- H0₁: There is no significant relationship between job creation and sustainable development in Nigeria.
H0₂: There is no significant relationship between economic progress and sustainable development in Nigeria.
H0₃: There is no significant relationship between wealth creation and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

Findings from this study provides valuable insights for business leaders and entrepreneurs on how to integrate sustainability into their operations and decision-making processes. By identifying practical

approaches, opportunities, and best practices, the research can help businesses align profitability with environmental stewardship and social responsibility, thus enhancing their competitiveness and long-term viability.

The study serves as an important resource for policymakers and development agencies by offering evidence-based recommendations that can inform the design of supportive regulatory frameworks and incentive structures. It underscores the need for policies that encourage corporate accountability, innovation, and responsible business practices, which are essential for creating an enabling environment for sustainable growth.

The study serves as a secondary source of data for researchers/scholars who wish to carry out research on this area. The study will also be a step further in the body of existing knowledge on the role of business with its dimensions such as job creation, economic progress and wealth creation in promoting sustainable development in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Role of Business

According to Amah (2014), businesses play a crucial role in promoting sustainable development since they are the main drivers of social change, economic growth, innovation, and job creation. Companies in Nigeria are especially well-positioned to address these issues by incorporating sustainability goals into their operations, as the country's high unemployment, poverty, and environmental degradation regularly obstruct economic advancement. By funding inclusive business models, education, health, renewable energy, and infrastructure, the private sector can significantly aid in the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Adeleke et al., 2022).

Creating economic value while reducing adverse effects on the environment and society is one of the main responsibilities of enterprises. In addition to improving their reputation, businesses that embrace sustainable practices like waste minimisation, energy efficiency, and moral labour standards also support long-term national growth (Okonkwo & Udeh, 2021). Businesses in the oil and manufacturing industries, for instance, that make investments in pollution prevention strategies and clean technology contribute to the preservation of natural ecosystems and enhance the health of local populations. Sustainable growth requires a stable and productive society, which is what these initiatives promote.

Additionally, companies use their marketing, merchandise, and CSR programmes to affect customer behaviour and society ideals. Businesses foster more social consciousness and civic duty when they support sustainable consumption and community development (Obi & Afolabi, 2022). Furthermore, by assisting small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) through supply chain collaborations and capacity-building initiatives, big businesses may act as engines for inclusive growth (Adegbite & Nakajima, 2020). By incorporating social, environmental, and economic factors into their fundamental plans and operations, businesses in Nigeria may significantly contribute to the advancement of sustainable development. This strategy supports both national and international development goals in addition to ensuring long-term profitability.

Dimensions

There are several dimensions of the role of business, based on this study, the following dimensions was considered: Job creation, economic progress and wealth creation.

Job Creation

One of the most important aspects of business's involvement in advancing sustainable development is the creation of jobs, particularly in developing nations like Nigeria. The greatest employer of workers in Nigeria is the private sector, especially small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), which also plays a significant role in raising living standards and lowering unemployment. Businesses contribute to poverty reduction, social inclusion, and economic growth by creating job opportunities—all of which are critical elements of sustainable development (Akinyemi & Alege, 2021). Businesses' capacity to generate employment has a significant impact in a nation where young unemployment is still a significant

socioeconomic issue. Businesses assist indirect job creation through their value chains and business connections in addition to directly creating jobs. For instance, large firms often rely on networks of local suppliers, logistics providers, and service firms, thereby creating additional employment opportunities across different sectors of the economy (Agbo & Olabisi, 2022). The multiplier effect of job creation is significant, as employed individuals can support families, pay taxes, and contribute to national development.

Additionally, companies that make training and upskilling investments in human capital development contribute to the growth of a more skilled staff, which raises innovation and productivity. In order to fill skill shortages and equip people ready for the changing needs of the labour market, several organisations in Nigeria now run workforce development programmes that target recent graduates, craftspeople, and female entrepreneurs (Nwosu & Olowookere, 2022). In addition to encouraging economic inclusion, these programmes help communities become more resilient and sustainable over the long run. Additionally, companies support better working conditions, job security, and employee well-being by encouraging decent work and fair labour practices. The Sustainable Development Goal 8, which prioritises full and productive employment, decent work for all, and inclusive and sustainable economic growth, is in line with responsible employment practices. Therefore, job creation is not just about quantity but also about quality ensuring that workers have access to fair wages, safe work environments, and opportunities for advancement (Okoye & Onwumere, 2023).

Economic Progress

Economic progress is a key dimension of the role of business in promoting sustainable development, particularly in a developing economy like Nigeria. Businesses contribute to economic progress through capital investment, innovation, increased productivity, and the efficient allocation of resources. By driving economic activities, the private sector plays a fundamental role in growing the gross domestic product (GDP), diversifying the economy, and enhancing national income. In Nigeria, where over-reliance on oil revenue has led to vulnerabilities, the diversification driven by private sector involvement in agriculture, manufacturing, information technology, and services is essential for long-term sustainability (Eze & Okpala, 2021).

Businesses serve as the backbone of economic progress by mobilizing financial and human capital to generate goods and services that meet societal needs. The establishment and expansion of industries foster local production, reduce dependence on imports, and stimulate exports, thereby improving the country's trade balance and foreign exchange earnings (Adeniran & Yusuf, 2020). For example, increased investment in the agro-processing sector has enhanced value addition, created supply chain linkages, and opened access to both domestic and international markets.

Moreover, business activities generate tax revenues that fund public infrastructure and social services. The taxes paid by private firms support government investment in education, healthcare, roads, and power, which are crucial enablers of economic development. As businesses thrive and expand, their contribution to the national treasury increases, allowing for broader public investment and fiscal stability (Obasi & Ayoola, 2022). Additionally, private sector-led research and development promote innovation, technological advancement, and entrepreneurship all of which contribute to economic dynamism and competitiveness.

Furthermore, by encouraging investment in underserved regions and promoting inclusive economic participation, businesses contribute to reducing regional disparities and fostering balanced growth. Inclusive business models that integrate low-income populations as producers, employees, and consumers play a vital role in lifting communities out of poverty and building economic resilience (Chukwu & Ugochukwu, 2022). These inclusive approaches align with the broader objectives of sustainable development by ensuring that economic progress benefits all segments of society. Businesses are pivotal in shaping Nigeria's economic trajectory. Their role in stimulating production, creating value, paying taxes, and encouraging innovation underscores their importance as agents of economic transformation and sustainable development.

Wealth Creation

Wealth creation is a fundamental dimension of the role of business in promoting sustainable development, as it directly influences the distribution of income, capital formation, and overall economic empowerment. In the Nigerian context, businesses serve as key agents in generating wealth not only for their owners and shareholders but also for employees, suppliers, and communities. Through the production of goods and services, investment in value chains, and provision of income-generating opportunities, businesses help individuals and households accumulate assets and improve their standards of living (Ibrahim & Afolayan, 2022).

The wealth created by businesses fuels a cycle of economic activity that leads to broader prosperity. For instance, when businesses make profits, they reinvest in expansion, technology, and infrastructure, thereby increasing productivity and creating more value. This reinvestment drives innovation and competitiveness, which further enhances their capacity to create wealth. At the same time, workers earn wages, entrepreneurs generate profits, and governments collect taxes all of which contribute to broader wealth distribution and national development (Olumide & Ajayi, 2021).

In addition, businesses promote entrepreneurship, which is a powerful tool for wealth creation. Nigeria's vibrant informal and SME sectors show that with access to capital and markets, many citizens can create and grow their own enterprises. This form of economic participation fosters self-reliance and reduces dependence on government or foreign aid. Empowering people through business opportunities encourages sustainable livelihoods, community development, and intergenerational wealth transfer, especially in rural areas (Uchenna & Ugo, 2023). Moreover, by engaging in inclusive business models that integrate low-income groups as stakeholders, businesses contribute to reducing inequality and fostering equitable wealth creation. Initiatives such as microfinance, cooperative businesses, and fair trade practices allow marginalized populations to participate meaningfully in economic activities. When businesses prioritize social value alongside profit, they foster an ecosystem where wealth is more evenly distributed and development is more inclusive (Balogun & Ekundayo, 2022).

Sustainable Development

Sustainable development, defined as meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs, is a crucial dimension of the role of business in contemporary society. In Nigeria, businesses are increasingly recognized not just for their profit-making capacity, but also for their potential to drive long-term environmental, social, and economic well-being. By integrating sustainability into their core strategies, businesses can help tackle pressing development challenges such as poverty, inequality, environmental degradation, and weak institutional capacity (Okeke & Iwuchukwu, 2022).

Businesses contribute to sustainable development by adopting practices that minimize negative environmental impacts. For example, companies in the manufacturing, oil, and energy sectors in Nigeria are investing in cleaner technologies, efficient resource management, and waste reduction measures. These efforts are essential in reducing carbon emissions, protecting biodiversity, and conserving water and energy resources. Sustainable business practices also involve responsible sourcing, green supply chain management, and investment in renewable energy (Adebayo & Musa, 2021). These initiatives help mitigate the adverse effects of industrial activities and contribute to a healthier environment.

Socially, businesses promote sustainable development by advancing corporate social responsibility (CSR), community engagement, and human capital development. Many Nigerian firms invest in education, health care, youth empowerment, and women's economic inclusion. These social investments help build resilient communities, reduce inequality, and improve the quality of life. Furthermore, ethical labor practices, diversity and inclusion policies, and fair treatment of stakeholders reflect a company's commitment to social sustainability (Ekanem & Abiola, 2023).

Economically, sustainable development requires inclusive growth that benefits all segments of society. Businesses help achieve this by creating decent jobs, promoting entrepreneurship, and supporting local suppliers. In doing so, they strengthen local economies and ensure that economic progress is shared equitably. Additionally, businesses that embrace sustainability often gain competitive advantage, enhance

their reputation, and attract socially conscious investors and customers, thus reinforcing the business case for sustainable practices (Lawal & Ogunyemi, 2022). Sustainable development is an essential dimension of business responsibility in Nigeria. By aligning their operations with environmental stewardship, social impact, and economic inclusion, businesses play a transformative role in achieving long-term national and global development goals.

Theoretical Review

The study was anchored on Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory propounded by Elkington (1997)

Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory

Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory, introduced by Elkington (1997), expands the traditional measure of business success to include three performance dimensions: **People (social), Planet (environment), and Profit (economic)**. This theory encourages businesses to operate in a manner that balances economic growth with social equity and environmental sustainability. For Nigerian businesses, adopting the TBL approach means integrating social responsibility initiatives (such as health and education programs), reducing environmental footprints (e.g., waste management and green energy), and ensuring long-term economic value creation. The TBL theory thus provides a practical framework for assessing the broader impact of business activities on sustainable development.

Assumptions of Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory

The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory, introduced by John Elkington in 1997, assumes that sustainable business performance should be evaluated not just by financial outcomes (profit), but also by social (people) and environmental (planet) impacts. The theory is built upon the following key assumptions:

1. **Businesses have multidimensional responsibilities:** TBL assumes that companies are not only responsible to shareholders but also to a broader group of stakeholders including employees, customers, communities, and the environment. Profitability alone is insufficient for evaluating a company's success; it must also contribute positively to society and minimize its ecological footprint.
2. **Economic, social, and environmental goals can coexist:** The theory assumes that organizations can pursue financial gains while simultaneously promoting social equity and environmental stewardship. These three pillars are interdependent, and long-term business success is achievable only when there is balance among them.
3. **Sustainability is measurable and reportable:** TBL assumes that social and environmental impacts can be tracked, quantified, and reported just like financial results. This leads to the growing use of sustainability reports, environmental audits, and social impact assessments in corporate accountability frameworks.
4. **Long-term value creation is superior to short-term profit maximization:** TBL promotes the assumption that businesses focused on long-term sustainability are more resilient and valuable in the long run than those driven solely by immediate profits. Ethical and sustainable practices build trust, loyalty, and stakeholder engagement.
5. **Stakeholder engagement is critical:** The theory assumes that businesses must regularly engage with stakeholders to understand their expectations and integrate them into corporate strategies. Open dialogue with stakeholders supports transparency and collaborative problem-solving.
6. **Regeneration, not just mitigation:** TBL assumes that businesses should not only minimize their negative impacts but actively contribute to restoring and regenerating environmental and social systems, thus creating net positive outcomes.

Implication/Relevance of Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory to the Study

The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Theory is relevant to this study as it provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing the multifaceted role of business in promoting sustainable development in Nigeria. By emphasizing the integration of economic performance (profit), social responsibility (people), and environmental stewardship (planet), the TBL theory aligns closely with the objectives of this study, which seeks to explore how businesses contribute not only to economic growth but also to social progress and environmental sustainability. In a developing country like Nigeria, where poverty, unemployment, and

environmental degradation are pressing challenges, the TBL framework enables a balanced evaluation of business practices beyond traditional profit metrics, offering insights into how corporate strategies can align with national and global development goals such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Empirical Review

Ogunyemi (2024) explored the determinants of sustainable development in Nigeria from 1981 to 2022, using the Adjusted Net Savings Rate (ANS) as a proxy for sustainable development and examining variables such as GDP per capita, total natural rent, unemployment rate, inflation rate, and terms of trade. To analyze the data, the study employed Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) and Granger Causality tests to identify determinants and causality directions among the variables. The findings highlighted a sustained long-term relationship between these factors, with GDP per capita and total natural rents emerging as key determinants of sustainable development. In contrast, the inflation rate, terms of trade, and unemployment rate were found to have no significant impact. The results also revealed bidirectional causality between sustainable development and GDP per capita, unidirectional causality between terms of trade and total natural resource revenue with sustainable development, and no causality between unemployment rate and inflation rate with sustainable development. The study recommends promoting economic development alongside increased savings and implementing fiscal policies to reduce public deficits as strategies to enhance sustainable development in Nigeria.

Eze and Okonkwo (2021) examined the contribution of corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives to sustainable development among manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study aimed to assess how CSR practices such as environmental protection, community development, and employee welfare impact sustainable development outcomes. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, and the study targeted 250 staff members from five selected manufacturing companies. A sample size of 150 respondents was determined using proportionate stratified sampling. Data were gathered through structured questionnaires and analyzed using multiple regression analysis via SPSS. The findings revealed that CSR initiatives, especially those focused on environmental protection and community health, significantly contribute to sustainable development. The study concluded that manufacturing firms have a vital role in addressing environmental and social issues through strategic CSR engagement. The authors recommended that businesses should embed sustainability principles into their core strategies and increase investment in community-based programs that align with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Ibrahim and Yusuf (2022) explored the impact of green business practices on environmental sustainability in the Nigerian telecommunications sector. The study focused on how eco-friendly innovations, energy-efficient technologies, and e-waste management influence the sector's environmental footprint. Employing a cross-sectional survey design, the researchers sampled 300 employees across three major telecom firms in Abuja. Convenience sampling was used to select 180 valid respondents. Data were collected through a semi-structured questionnaire and analyzed using inferential statistics, including ANOVA and regression analysis. The results showed a strong positive relationship between the adoption of green business practices and environmental sustainability outcomes. The study concluded that telecom companies can play a significant role in mitigating environmental degradation through sustainable practices. The researchers recommended that firms should intensify their environmental awareness campaigns, adopt cleaner technologies, and strengthen internal sustainability policies to enhance long-term ecological resilience.

Gap in Literature

A review of existing literature reveals that several studies have examined aspects of business contributions to sustainable development in Nigeria, focusing largely on corporate social responsibility (CSR), green practices, and macroeconomic indicators. For example, Eze and Okonkwo (2021) concentrated on the CSR practices of manufacturing firms, while Ibrahim and Yusuf (2022) explored green business practices within the telecommunications sector. Ogunyemi (2024) adopted a

macroeconomic lens to analyze determinants of sustainable development using national-level economic data. While these studies provide valuable insights into sector-specific practices and national trends, they fall short in presenting a comprehensive framework that connects business activities particularly job creation, economic progress, and wealth creation with sustainable development at a multidimensional level.

Furthermore, most of the reviewed literature tends to focus on either environmental or corporate social aspects of business involvement in sustainability, often neglecting how these roles function in synergy with economic dimensions such as employment generation, income distribution, and local enterprise support. The studies also offer limited perspectives on how small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) which constitute the bulk of Nigeria’s private sector contribute to sustainable development beyond CSR initiatives.

This current study addresses these gaps by offering an integrated analysis of the role of business in promoting sustainable development through the specific lenses of job creation, economic progress, and wealth creation. It goes beyond general CSR and environmental practices to examine how these economic functions of businesses directly and indirectly influence national development outcomes. In doing so, the study seeks to contribute a more nuanced and holistic understanding of the business-sustainability nexus within the Nigerian, thereby offering practical and policy-relevant insights for stakeholders in both the public and private sectors.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study refers to the group of individuals or subjects that are the focus of a research investigation. It is the specific group that the researchers aim to gather data from and draw conclusions about in order to answer research questions. According to the *National Survey of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Nigeria, 2017* report, which is the most recent comprehensive survey providing state-level breakdowns, Rivers State had 1,150,000 MSMEs as of 2017. Therefore, the population of the study was 1,150,000 businesses in Rivers State. The sample size of 400 was determined using Taro Yamane Statistical Tool. Purposive sampling techniques was adopted. Structured questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was developed in line with four point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) in accordance with the three research questions raised in the study. A total of 400 copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents. 283 copies representing 71% were retrieved while 117 copies representing 29% were not retrieved. The data which was gathered from the field was analysed using mean and standard deviation. All tests for the study was carried out using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The hypotheses were tested using Spearman’s Rank order correlation coefficient at a significance level of 0.05. This statistical tool was selected based on its flexibility and non-specification or emphasis of parameters or statistical assumptions in the determination of associations. The tool was also considered appropriate for data that is scaled on the ordinal as well as interval scale.

DATA PRESENTATION

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the role of job creation on sustainable development in Nigeria

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Job creation by businesses contributes to poverty reduction in Nigeria.	283	1.00	4.00	2.3004	1.06103
Job creation helps in reducing crime and social unrest.	283	1.00	4.00	2.3039	1.03805
Businesses in Nigeria are major contributors to youth employment.	283	1.00	4.00	2.1979	1.06345
Valid N (listwise)	283				

Source: Field Data, 2025

The descriptive statistics indicates that respondents generally perceive job creation as an important factor in promoting sustainable development in Nigeria. The mean values for all three items ranging between 2.19 and 2.30 on a scale where lower values suggest stronger agreement reflect a moderately positive perception of the role of job creation. Respondents acknowledge that job creation contributes to poverty reduction, helps reduce crime and social unrest, and that businesses play a significant role in youth employment. The relatively low standard deviations (around 1.06) suggest a fair level of consistency in responses across the sample. The data suggest that job creation is viewed as a key mechanism through which businesses support sustainable development in Nigeria.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on the role of economic progress on sustainable development in Nigeria

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Economic progress is essential for achieving sustainable development in Nigeria.	283	1.00	4.00	2.3145	.99111
Economic progress promotes social welfare and quality of life.	283	1.00	4.00	2.0777	1.03192
Technological advancements by businesses support national development goals.	283	1.00	4.00	2.4523	1.07206
Valid N (listwise)	283				

Source: Field Data, 2025

The descriptive statistics reveal that respondents hold a generally favorable view of economic progress as a driver of sustainable development in Nigeria. The mean scores, which range from approximately 2.08 to 2.45, indicate a moderate level of agreement with the statements that economic progress enhances social welfare, contributes to sustainable development, and is supported by technological advancements from businesses. The lowest mean (2.08) reflects strong agreement that economic progress promotes social welfare and quality of life, suggesting this is a particularly valued outcome among respondents. The standard deviations, all slightly above or below 1.0, show a moderate level of variability in responses. Collectively, the data underscore the belief that economic progress through development, welfare, and technology is a significant contributor to sustainable development in Nigeria.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on the role of wealth creation on sustainable development in Nigeria

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Business-led wealth creation supports entrepreneurship and innovation.	283	1.00	4.00	1.9223	.89974
Wealth generated by businesses improves living standards and quality of life.	283	1.00	4.00	2.0742	1.02008
Wealth creation contributes to community development through social investment.	283	1.00	4.00	2.0035	.95464
Valid N (listwise)	283				

Source: Field Data, 2025

The descriptive statistics suggest that respondents strongly agree on the positive role of wealth creation in promoting sustainable development in Nigeria. The mean scores, ranging from approximately 1.92 to 2.07, indicate a high level of agreement that business-led wealth creation supports entrepreneurship and innovation, improves living standards, and contributes to community development through social investment. Notably, the lowest mean (1.92) reflects particularly strong support for the link between wealth creation and entrepreneurship. The standard deviations, all below 1.05, indicate a relatively low variability in responses, suggesting a consistent perception among respondents. Overall, the data highlight that wealth creation is widely recognized as a critical enabler of inclusive and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on Sustainable Development

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Sustainable development is necessary for Nigeria's economic growth.	283	1.00	4.00	2.3039	1.03805
Job creation initiatives align with sustainable development goals.	283	1.00	4.00	2.1979	1.06345
Corruption is a major barrier to sustainable development in Nigeria.	283	1.00	4.00	2.3145	.99111
Valid N (listwise)	283				

Source: Field Data, 2025

The descriptive statistics indicate that respondents generally agree on the importance and relevance of sustainable development in Nigeria. The mean scores, which range from approximately 2.19 to 2.31 on a 4-point scale, suggest a moderately strong agreement across all three statements. Respondents recognized sustainable development as essential for Nigeria's economic growth, supported the alignment of job creation initiatives with sustainable development goals, and acknowledged corruption as a significant barrier. The lowest mean (2.1979) corresponds to agreement that job creation aligns with sustainable development, highlighting its perceived strategic relevance. The relatively consistent standard deviations, all around 1.0, suggest moderate variability in opinions but an overall consensus that sustainable development is both necessary and challenged by systemic issues such as corruption. These findings affirm the critical role of sustainability-focused business and governance reforms in Nigeria's long-term development agenda.

Test of Hypotheses

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between job creation and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Table 5: Correlations between Job creation and Sustainable Development

		Job Creation	Sustainable Development
Spearman's rho	Job creation	1.000	.539
	Correlation Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
	N	283	283
Sustainable Development	Correlation Coefficient	.539	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
	N	283	283

The correlation analysis using Spearman's rho reveals a moderate positive relationship between job creation and sustainable development, with a correlation coefficient of **0.539**. This suggests that as job creation by businesses increases, there is a corresponding increase in sustainable development outcomes. The **p-value of 0.001** (less than 0.05) indicates that the relationship is statistically significant, meaning the observed correlation is unlikely to have occurred by chance.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between economic progress and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Table 6: Correlations between economic progress and sustainable development

		Economic Progress	Sustainable Development
Spearman's rho	Economic Progress	Correlation Coefficient	1.000 .676
		Sig. (2-tailed)	. .003
		N	283 283
Sustainable Development		Correlation Coefficient	.676 1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.003 .
		N	283 283

The Spearman's rho correlation analysis shows a strong positive relationship between economic progress and sustainable development, with a correlation coefficient of **0.676**. This indicates that improvements in economic progress such as increased investment, innovation, and productivity are significantly associated with better sustainable development outcomes in Nigeria. The **p-value of 0.003**, which is less than the 0.05 threshold, confirms that this relationship is statistically significant. With a sample size of 283, the findings suggest that economic progress is a critical driver of sustainable development, reinforcing the importance of private sector growth and investment in achieving long-term national development goals.

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between wealth creation and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Table 7: Correlations between wealth creation and sustainable development

		Wealth Creation	Sustainable Development
Spearman's rho	Wealth Creation	Correlation Coefficient	1.000 .573
		Sig. (2-tailed)	. .002
		N	283 283
sustainable Development		Correlation Coefficient	.573 1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.002 .
		N	283 283

The Spearman's rho correlation analysis reveals a moderate positive relationship between wealth creation and sustainable development, with a correlation coefficient of **0.573**. This indicates that as businesses create more wealth through investment, entrepreneurship, and income generation there is a corresponding improvement in sustainable development outcomes in Nigeria. The **p-value of 0.002**, which is below the 0.05 significance level, confirms that the relationship is statistically significant and not due to random chance. With a sample size of 283, the findings underscore that wealth creation is a key factor contributing to inclusive and long-term development, highlighting the role of businesses in promoting economic equity and social progress.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Creation and Sustainable Development

The findings indicate that job creation is widely perceived as a crucial factor in driving sustainable development in Nigeria. Respondents affirmed that job creation by businesses contributes to poverty reduction, helps reduce crime and social unrest, and plays a major role in youth employment. These perceptions align with the work of Akinyemi and Alege (2021), who asserted that private sector-led employment is a significant pathway to inclusive growth in Nigeria. Similarly, Agbo and Olabisi (2022)

emphasized the multiplier effect of employment creation on poverty alleviation and social stability. The consistency in responses also supports the notion that job creation not only addresses economic concerns but also has social implications, such as reducing crime and enhancing societal cohesion. Moreover, the findings reflect Sustainable Development Goal 8, which promotes decent work and economic growth. This reinforces the argument by Okoye and Onwumere (2023) that responsible employment practices contribute to national productivity and stability. Hence, the findings affirm that job creation is not only a key economic function of business but also a critical element of sustainable development in Nigeria.

Economic Progress and Sustainable Development

The study revealed that economic progress is strongly associated with sustainable development. Respondents agreed that economic advancement enhances social welfare, supports technological innovation, and is essential for achieving development goals. These findings are consistent with Eze and Okpala (2021), who emphasized that economic diversification through private sector initiatives enhances national resilience and long-term sustainability. The positive response regarding the role of technology in development supports Adeniran and Yusuf's (2020) assertion that private sector innovation contributes to economic dynamism. The agreement among respondents further confirms the position of Obasi and Ayoola (2022) that private investment and business growth improve infrastructure and public service delivery through tax contributions. Thus, the results validate the role of economic progress, driven by business activities, as a central pillar of sustainable development in Nigeria.

Wealth Creation and Sustainable Development

The findings highlight that respondents perceive wealth creation by businesses as a powerful driver of sustainable development. The highest agreement was seen in statements linking wealth creation to entrepreneurship, improved living standards, and community development. These findings align with Ibrahim and Afolayan (2022), who noted that wealth generated by business activities promotes financial independence and intergenerational economic stability. Additionally, Uchenna and Ugo (2023) emphasized that entrepreneurship, often fueled by wealth reinvestment, is a key engine of inclusive economic growth in Nigeria. Balogun and Ekundayo (2022) further argue that inclusive wealth creation models such as microfinance and cooperative enterprises enable marginalized groups to participate in and benefit from economic activities. The current findings therefore confirm that wealth creation, especially when inclusive, significantly contributes to sustainable development by empowering individuals, promoting equity, and strengthening local economies. These results reinforce the broader call for businesses to integrate social value creation with profit-making in order to build a more inclusive and resilient Nigerian society.

CONCLUSION

The study examined the role of business in promoting sustainable development in Nigeria, focusing on three key dimensions: job creation, economic progress, and wealth creation. The findings reveal that businesses significantly influence sustainable development by generating employment opportunities, stimulating economic growth, and facilitating inclusive wealth distribution. The analysis shows that job creation not only reduces poverty and unemployment but also contributes to social stability and national productivity. Economic progress driven by private sector innovation, investment, and diversification plays a pivotal role in advancing infrastructure, improving social welfare, and fostering long-term national development. Additionally, wealth creation by businesses especially when inclusive empowers individuals and communities, promotes entrepreneurship, and reduces inequality, all of which are essential components of sustainable development. The role of business in sustainable development is not optional but essential. A sustainable future for Nigeria requires active collaboration between businesses, government, and civil society to ensure economic growth, social equity, and environmental protection are pursued in harmony for the benefit of present and future generations.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations was made among others that:

1. Government and business leaders should collaborate to expand job opportunities through support for small and medium enterprises.
2. Policymakers should create a stable and conducive business environment through infrastructure development.
3. Government and financial institutions should also provide access to credit and financial services for entrepreneurs, particularly women and rural dwellers, to promote economic inclusion.

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